

International transfers of health research data following Schrems II: A problem in need of a solution

Dara Hallinan¹, Alexander Bernier², Anne Cambon-Thomsen³, Francis P. Crawley⁴, Diana Dimitrova⁵, Claudia Bauzer Medeiros⁶, Gustav Nilsson⁷, Simon Parker⁸, Brian Pickering⁹, Stéphanie Rennes¹⁰.

Abstract

On July 16th 2020, the Court of Justice of the European Union issued a landmark decision in the case of *Data Protection Commissioner v. Facebook Ireland Ltd, Maximillian Schrems (Schrems II)* concerning the legality of Facebook's transfers of personal data from the EU to the US. The decision has potentially significant effects on the ability of researchers to legitimately transfer personal data for health research purposes from countries inside the EU, to third countries outside the EU.¹¹ This article aims: i) to outline the consequences of the *Schrems II* decision for the legitimate sharing of personal data for health research between the EU and third countries, particularly in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic; and, in light of this elaboration, ii) to consider the avenues that might be pursued to remedy challenges posed by the decision and to facilitate international data exchange for health research moving forward.

¹ Corresponding author: Dara Hallinan, FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur, Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344, Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany, dara.hallinan@fiz-karlsruhe.de, ORCID: 0000-0002-1160-821X.

² Alexander Bernier, McGill University Faculty of Medicine, Centre of Genomics and Policy, alexander.bernier@mail.mcgill.ca, ORCID: 0000-0001-8615-8375.

³ Anne Cambon-Thomsen, Inserm and University Toulouse III Paul Sabatier, Joint Unit 1027, Epidemiology and analyses in public health, Toulouse, France, anne.cambon-thomsen@univ-tlse3.fr, ORCID: 0000-0001-8793-3644.

⁴ Francis P. Crawley, Good Clinical Practice Alliance - Europe (GCPA) & Strategic Initiative for Developing Capacity in Ethical Review (SIDCER), Leuven, Belgium, fpc@gcpalliance.org, ORCID: 000-0002-6893-5916.

⁵ Diana Dimitrova, FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur, Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344, Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany, diana.dimitrova@fiz-karlsruhe.de.

⁶ Claudia Bauzer Medeiros, Institute of Computing, University of Campinas, Brazil, cmbm@ic.unicamp.br, ORCID: 0000-0003-1908-4753.

⁷ Gustav Nilsson, Karolinska Institutet, Department of Clinical Neuroscience, and University of Gothenburg, Swedish National Data Service, gustav.nilsson@ki.se.

⁸ Simon Parker, Cancer Research UK, simon.parker@cancer.org.uk, ORCID: 0000-0001-9993-533X.

⁹ Brian Pickering, University of Southampton, j.b.pickering@soton.ac.uk, ORCID: 0000-0002-6815-2938.

¹⁰ Stéphanie Rennes, INRAE, DAJ, 75007 Paris, France, and University of Strasbourg, University of Lorraine, CNRS, BETA, 67000 Strasbourg, France, stephanie.rennes@inrae.fr, ORCID: 0000-0003-1458-7773.

¹¹ The GDPR also has relevance in the European Economic Area (EEA). The analysis presented in this paper also has general relevance for all EEA countries. The EEA consists of all EU countries as well as Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway. Countries in the EEA are subject to certain EU law, albeit not all EU law. The relationship between the two groups of countries is complex and subject to numerous specific regulations. Accordingly, given that the GDPR is law promulgated by the EU, in the first place, the paper refers to the EU throughout the discussion to avoid the need for possible nuances with respect to the other EEA countries.

Keywords

EU Law, General Data Protection Regulation, Schrems II, Adequacy, Third Country Transfers, Health Research,

1. Introduction

Health research includes activities related to the production of scientific knowledge intended to improve the well-being of individuals, communities, and the public as a whole. (1)¹² Data necessary to support health research is often, however, collected and stored across a wide range of geographical and legal jurisdictions involving various stakeholders. This paper focuses on the effects of the Court of Justice of the European Union's (CJEU) *Schrems II* decision - in which the legality of Facebook's transfers of personal data from the EU to the US was addressed - on the exchange of personal data for health research purposes, specifically in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Processing data for health research often involves processing personal data. In order to facilitate the exchange of personal data across jurisdictional borders, certain states and supra-national organisations have elaborated special laws governing when, and under what conditions, data may be exchanged. The principal law elaborating the conditions governing the international transfer of personal data from EU Member States is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). (2)

This law provides various justifications for the transfer of personal data to third countries outside the EU. In practice, the law has generally functioned effectively as a framework used by EU researchers to transfer personal data outside the EU for health research purposes – albeit with

¹² We align our definitions with Frascati's terms.

certain exceptions.¹³ On July 16th 2020, the CJEU - Europe's highest court - issued its decision in the *Schrems II* case concerning the law on transfers of personal data from the EU to third countries.

(4)

In its decision, the court made several statements whose impact on health-related research transfers are likely to be dramatic. In the first instance, the court voided certain justifications – specifically the Privacy Shield decision which facilitated data transfers between the EU and the US. In turn, the court placed consequential limitations on the majority of other transfer justifications with broad applicability to, and utility for, health research – including, for example, Standard Contractual Clauses, Binding Corporate Rules (BCRs), and codes of conduct.

Against the background of this case, we aim: i) to outline the consequences of the *Schrems II* decision for the legitimate exchange of personal health data between the EU and third countries, specifically in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic; and ii), in light of this elaboration, to consider ways to address these consequences and facilitate international data exchange for health research moving forward.

We begin by describing the importance of international data exchange for health research (section 2). We continue by providing a brief overview of the justifications available under the GDPR for the legitimate transfer of personal data for health research from the EU to third countries (section 3). The discussion then moves to provide a more detailed overview of the *Schrems II* case and to look at how the decision in the case impacts the transfer of EU personal data for health research (sections 5 and 6).

¹³ *Peloquin et. al.* (3) for instance, highlighted certain difficulties in legitimating transfers to the U.S.

We then discuss possible ways to address the challenges posed to the exchange of personal data for health research by *Schrems II*. The article offers two approaches to meet these newly surfacing challenges. First, we highlight certain technological approaches that might allow third country researchers to legitimately analyse personal data stored in the EU where transfers are no longer legally possible (Section 7). We also, however, highlight a need for caution in considering these technological solutions as providing perfect answers (Section 8).

Second, we suggest that challenges may be overcome via the conclusion of international transfer agreements specific to health research between the EU and third countries. Such specific agreements would mirror the fact that the processing of personal data for health research purposes is treated as a unique case of data processing in EU law. In turn, in many cases, it seems likely the conclusion of such agreements would come with little disadvantage to other pertinent EU or third country interests, while bringing considerable advantages to health research (Section 9).

2. The Importance of International Data Exchange in Health Research

Health research is often an international endeavour. In this regard, at least three types of arguments outlining the importance of international data exchange of personal data for health research can be put forward.

First, several kinds of health research depend completely on the international exchange of personal data. Such research includes: research into questions best addressed by comparing data from multiple populations in distinct regions to determine whether conclusions based on a local population can be generalized; research which requires data sets from geographically specific target populations; and research which can only be effectively conducted with access to personal data sets located in multiple different countries. For example, multicentre treatment studies

involving treatment centres located in several different countries, as well as international task forces/interest groups devoted to the study of rare diseases - for which only limited patient populations may exist – may be completely dependent on being able to pool personal data across borders. (5)

Second, the optimal conduct of health research requires that personal data be as accessible as possible so that research can be synthesized and built upon. The redaction or anonymisation of data inevitably weakens the utility of the data. In the context of meta-analysis, use of individual patient data is considered a gold standard for estimating treatment effects. Equally, the availability of personal data can bring substantial improvements to the quality of data available, the analysis conducted, and the results obtained. In this regard, risks of bias can be assessed more thoroughly and in more detail. In addition, personal data permits flexible analysis, including reanalysis, through which research can be independently tested and verified with greater accuracy than would be possible with aggregate data or other forms of data assemblies.¹⁴ For instance, the use of personal data allows for the harmonization of measures, multivariate and other complex analyses and investigations of interactions between interventions and patient-level characteristics not possible with other forms of data assemblies. (7) Finally, the availability of personal data allows new scientific questions to be asked of existing data - including discovery, hypothesis generation, and external validation, for example of predictive models.

Finally, international data exchange serves ethical goals. In the first instance, international data exchange aids in research resourcing and collaboration. In repurposing existing data for novel research purposes, resources required to collect personal data are reduced. In turn, international

¹⁴ For instance, the recent scandal involving Surgisphere could have been prevented or exposed sooner if the personal data in question could have been examined at the outset by the researchers (6).

data exchange maximizes the contributions of individuals and institutions in the advancement of scientific knowledge and in the development of new health interventions. This can be particularly important given that contribution to health research can have an exacting toll - both physical and psychological - on research participants, communities, and society at large.¹⁵ Data sharing also brings researchers together into common projects and helps to break down the silos and boundaries that impair research and slow innovation. Finally, international data exchange facilitates the goal of equitable research. The aim of several recent initiatives has been to engage all actors – participants and researchers - across the data lifecycle, encouraging broader engagement, trust in scientific research, research transparency and the development of research capacity across the globe.¹⁶

The international exchange of personal data for health research, however, is subject to legal conditions. The law elaborating these conditions concerning transfers of personal data from the EU to third countries is the GDPR.

3. Sketching the General Approach of the GDPR to International Health Research Transfers from the EU

Under the GDPR, transfers of personal data from the EU to third countries are only legitimate if they are based on a justification outlined in the GDPR. The aim of each justification is to ensure that the standards of protection enjoyed by EU citizens concerning their personal data are

¹⁵ For example, cancer patients and their families contribute time and effort during the most difficult and strenuous period of their lives with no guarantee of personal benefit but in the hope of benefiting others in the future.

¹⁶ The CARE principles (8) for instance foreground the rights and expectations of both research participants and those involved in the collection of data. Beyond that, the principles also recommend that outcomes be shared with the engaged communities to encourage trust and future engagement. In essence, therefore, data sharing is about access to resources (data), which is often essential for access to research, which in turn is essential for access to medicines and other health interventions in many instances.

Related initiatives such as the Open Science Framework (9) and the FAIR principles (10) are aimed at making data accessible and seek to encourage participatory collaboration across the data lifecycle. At the European level, the final report of the Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP) has been released in 2020 (11). See also: (12).

maintained in the transfer to, and processing in, the third country to which data is transferred - i.e. the standard of protection and available redress is ‘essentially equivalent’ to that provided in the EU.¹⁷ The GDPR lists all possible justifications in Articles 44 to 49. The GDPR organises these justifications into a three-tier hierarchy.¹⁸ In each tier, justifications relevant to legitimating transfers for health research purposes are identifiable.

Tier 1: adequacy decisions as described in Article 45. An adequacy decision is a decision from the European Commission asserting that the state of legal protection for personal data in a specific third country is ‘essentially equivalent’ to that outlined in the EU. Where an adequacy decision is in place, all transfers of personal data falling within the scope of the decision can proceed freely - subject, if relevant, to any conditions specifically listed in the decision. The Commission has, to date, only issued 12 active adequacy decisions - including, for example, a recent adequacy decision concerning Japan.¹⁹ It is unlikely this number will increase with any rapidity. As Kuner observes, the adequacy procedure is a lengthy and involved process that can take a number of years to complete, and it can be hard to separate the process from politics, making outcomes difficult to predict. (16)²⁰

In principle, adequacy decisions provide a framework for the transfers of personal data for the purposes of health research. Certain adequacy decisions, however, only apply to specific sectors within a third country. For example, the adequacy decision concerning Canada only concerns

¹⁷ This is the legal term used in the GDPR in Recital 104 concerning the level of protection that should be provided in a transfer. This is also the term used in CJEU case law, including numerous times in the *Schrems II* case. See paras 64, 65, 94, 96, 97, 105, 162, 178, 181, 185, 190, 191, 193, 197.

¹⁸ See also: (13) and (14).

¹⁹ Active adequacy decisions are currently in force concerning: ‘Andorra, Argentina, Canada (commercial organisations), Faroe Islands, Guernsey, Israel, Isle of Man, Japan, Jersey, New Zealand, Switzerland, Uruguay’ (15). At the time of writing, the list on the European Commission website has not been updated in light of the *Schrems II* ruling and still includes the Privacy Shield decision as an active adequacy decision.

²⁰ See also, for an example of politics in adequacy decisions: Laurence Peter (17).

commercial organisations. (18) As a consequence, such sector specific adequacy decisions may be of limited use to health researchers whose activities are outside, or extend beyond, the sector covered by the decision. (19) For example, transfers of personal data for health research to Canadian public research institutions could not rely on the framework provided by the EU-Canada adequacy decision. Transfers to Canadian public research institutions would thus need to rely on another form of legal justification.

Tier 2: transfers subject to appropriate arrangements. If an adequacy decision under Article 45 is not available for a third country, an EU researcher or researcher may transfer personal data for health research purposes on the basis of a bilateral or multilateral agreement with a third-country recipient, or recipients, in which the standard of protection elaborated by EU law is ensured in relation to the foreseen processing of the data. Article 46 outlines several such justifications potentially relevant for health research: ‘a legally binding and enforceable instrument between public authorities’; ‘binding corporate rules’ - sets of agreements outlining data processing rules valid within a company or group of companies; ‘data protection clauses’ - contractual clauses concerning data transfer; ‘codes of conduct’; ‘certification mechanisms’; and ‘provisions . . . inserted into administrative arrangements between public authorities’.

Tier 3: specific situations. If neither an adequacy decision nor any of the forms of transfer subject to appropriate arrangements is available, then an EU researcher may transfer data to a third country on the basis of a range of other ‘specific situation’ justifications outlined in Article 49. The Article elaborates several justifications that may have relevance for health research transfers, including: if the research participant ‘has explicitly consented to the proposed transfer’; ‘the transfer is necessary for important reasons of public interest’; ‘the transfer is necessary in order to protect the

vital interests of the data subject or of other persons’; and the transfer ‘is necessary for the purposes of compelling legitimate interests pursued by the controller which are not overridden by the interests or rights and freedoms of the data subject’.

The general approach of the GDPR, however, is subject to supplemental clarifications concerning its implementation, as well as the interpretation of its constituent articles and clauses, via administrative and jurisprudential bodies. Recently, an important judicial decision was taken in the *Schrems II* case – the decision at the core of our discussion. A brief recap of the facts of the case, the logic of the decision, and its significance for health research transfers is in order.

4. *Schrems II*: The case, the decision, and health research transfers from the EU

On July 16th 2020, the CJEU handed down its judgment in *Data Protection Commissioner v. Facebook Ireland Ltd, Maximilian Schrems*. The *Schrems II* case builds on a previous decision on a similar topic, involving the same lead complainant, in 2015, which brought down the EU-US Safe Harbour Agreement (the so-called ‘*Schrems I*’ case).²¹

The facts of the *Schrems II* case and the legal procedures that led to the decision are complex. Put simply, however, the case concerns the question of how Facebook might legitimately transfer personal data from the EU to the US under the GDPR. In this regard, the case specifically dealt with two forms of transfer justification: i) the Privacy Shield agreement - a form of Article 45 adequacy decision for self-certified US corporate actors who fulfil certain requirements (21); and ii) Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs) - a form of Article 46 data protection contractual clause, the contents of which have been pre-approved by the European Commission. (22) The key question

²¹ See, for the previous case (20)

addressed in the case concerned whether these justifications could be relied upon in light of the fact that the US legal system permits mass surveillance operations, under which US intelligence agencies can access personal data transferred from the EU, with few limitations, and no guarantee of judicial redress for EU citizens who believe their fundamental rights may have been violated.

In its evaluation, the CJEU found that the US legal system did not provide a level of protection 'essentially equivalent' to that provided by the EU, as regards US intelligence agencies' powers to access and analyse, in bulk, EU citizens' transferred personal data. In particular, the CJEU highlighted two problems with the US legal system's approach: i) the possibility for intelligence agencies to collect and analyse EU citizens' transferred personal data was unnecessarily broad and included inadequate safeguards designed to protect data subjects' rights;²² and ii) the judicial review and redress mechanisms available to EU citizens concerning intelligence agencies' access to data did not meet the standards required by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.²³

For these reasons, the CJEU made two specific pronouncements that are also of consequence for health research transfers. First, the Privacy Shield adequacy decision was found to be illegitimate and was invalidated in its entirety with immediate effect. Consequently, there is now no active adequacy agreement capable of legitimating health research transfers between the EU and the US.

²² See, for example, para 180, concerning Privacy Shield: 'It is thus apparent that Section 702 of the FISA does not indicate any limitations on the power it confers to implement surveillance programmes for the purposes of foreign intelligence or the existence of guarantees for non-US persons potentially targeted by those programmes. In those circumstances . . . that article cannot ensure a level of protection essentially equivalent to that guaranteed by the Charter, as interpreted by the case-law set out in paragraphs 175 and 176 above, according to which a legal basis which permits interference with fundamental rights must, in order to satisfy the requirements of the principle of proportionality, itself define the scope of the limitation on the exercise of the right concerned and lay down clear and precise rules governing the scope and application of the measure in question and imposing minimum safeguards.'

²³ See, for example, para 187 concerning Privacy Shield: 'the Privacy Shield Decision cannot ensure a level of protection essentially equivalent to that arising from the Charter, contrary to the requirement in Article 45(2)(a) of the GDPR that a finding of equivalence depends, inter alia, on whether data subjects whose personal data are being transferred to the third country in question have effective and enforceable rights.'

Secondly, the SCCs outlined by the Commission are, in principle, still valid and useful to legitimate transfers of personal data for health research from the EU to third countries - including the US - but only provided that EU citizens' rights in relation to the specifics of the transfer(s) in question are provided with an 'essentially equivalent' standard of protection in the third country. Consequently, SCCs can only be used to legitimate health research transfers if: i) transferees' countries already provide 'essentially equivalent' protection for EU citizens' fundamental rights; or ii) other supplementary measures serving to protect EU citizens' rights in the third country – contractual, technical, organisational, or otherwise - can be put in place.²⁴

Beyond the specific pronouncements made by the court, however, the decision also has much broader implications for international health research transfers.

5. The Broader Consequences of *Schrems II* for International Health Research Transfers from the EU

Three broader consequences relevant to health research transfers deserve further discussion and elaboration.

First, whilst *Schrems II* dealt specifically with the Privacy Shield adequacy decision and the SCC justification, the logic of the decision also directly impacts the utility of all other tier-two transfer options for health research. In discussing the use of SCCs, the CJEU made clear that, in order to legitimately transfer personal data from the EU, the legal framework operative in a third country cannot function such that the overall standard of protection provided to EU citizens - apart from the bilateral agreement and any additional supplemental measures implemented by the transferee

²⁴ Quite which supplementary measures could help to make transfers appropriate, and how these relate to different legal contexts in third countries, remains unclear. EDPB guidance on this issue is to be expected in the coming months. See: (23).

- falls below the standard provided under EU law. In terms of their relationship with third country law, all other tier-two justifications function in a similar way to SCCs. There is thus no reason that basic requirements concerning the use of SCCs and third country laws should not apply to all other tier-two options.

The practical consequence of the above is that, whilst previously researchers might have sought to rely on uniform approaches – for example uniform data transfer agreements – under tier-two justifications for transferring personal data from the EU to third countries, this is no longer possible. Rather, researchers will now need to assess, on a case-by-case basis: i) if the country of destination is capable of providing a standard of protection ‘essentially equivalent’ to that provided in the EU; and if not ii) whether supplemental safeguards can be implemented in the specific case such that equivalence is ensured in another way. As the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) expressed, commenting on the case: ‘[controllers] should assess whether [they] can provide . . . measures to ensure an essentially equivalent level of protection as provided in the [EU], and if the law of the third country will not impinge on these supplementary measures so as to prevent their effectiveness.’(23)

From a policy standpoint, such a shift may require researchers to expend significant supplemental resources in conducting the relevant assessments needed to ensure legitimate transfers under tier-two justifications. This may constitute a significant obstacle to international health research. Certain researchers may not possess the resources required to perform the assessments. Other researchers may be dissuaded from taking on the risk of assessments, given the potentially significant financial penalties that can be imposed if transfer activities are eventually held to be non-compliant with the GDPR - including, for example, the significant fines which can be imposed

under Article 83(5). Even researchers that do possess the relevant resources and are not averse to the risk of engaging in transfers will need to engage in cost-benefit analyses as to whether to divert resources - that could otherwise be used for scientific activities - to engage in the conduct of the necessary assessments.

Second, whilst the case specifically considered the standard of protection provided in US law, the decision is also relevant for transfers to other third countries. Several other third countries have already been highlighted as potentially providing a standard of protection that may not be regarded as 'essentially equivalent' to that outlined in EU law. Some of these third countries - even including some with an adequacy decision, such as Canada - engage in mass surveillance practices similar to those highlighted as problematic in the US.²⁵ Still other third countries have been suggested to be problematic as a result of other forms of legislation, or as a result of the practical function of law in their society. Slokenberga et al., for example, discussing biobanking, highlight the fact that the standard of protection provided in certain African states might not reach that required by EU law. (31)

Third, the case has reintroduced the problem of international data transfers into the sphere of active public and political debate. The underlying problems highlighted by the case are not new, namely, that third countries hold divergent perspectives as to the expected standard of data protection from those of the EU and that these divergences, on occasion, may lead to a lower level of protection in these countries. Indeed, the specific problems highlighted by the CJEU in relation to a Privacy Shield decision have been raised repeatedly over the past years.²⁶ Prior to the case, these problems

²⁵ See, for example, in relation to Canada (24,25); and in relation to the UK (26). The Parliament make reference to CJEU case law in which UK national security legislation outlining bulk surveillance practices was considered (27): See, for example, in relation to China (28,29,30).

²⁶ See, for example (32).

had been addressed either with superficial legalistic solutions (such as that the use of SCCs alone serve to provide suitable protection) or, outside limited academic and political discussion, had been ignored rather than substantively addressed.²⁷ Following the *Schrems II* case, these underlying problems have been rudely exposed. The problems are now no longer subject to superficial legalistic resolution. They cannot be ignored.

One retort to our assertion that the consequences of the decision are significant for health research transfers might be: all the international transfer options outlined by non-US adequacy agreements as well as those in Article 49 (third-tier options) are untouched by the decision and the decision is therefore unproblematic. This retort is understandable. It is also, unfortunately, fatally flawed. In relation to other adequacy decisions, the fatal flaw is obvious: there are very few adequacy decisions currently in force and these can serve only to legitimate a limited set of transfers, few of which relate to the larger trading and scientific powers in the world. In relation to Article 49 options, however, a deeper elaboration of the flaws in the assertion is warranted.

6. Article 49 Options and their Limitations for Research Transfers

There are indeed several Article 49 justifications which, in the absence of an adequacy decision or the ability to rely on a tier-two justification, may serve to legitimate health research transfers. A deeper look at the conditions under which these justifications may be applicable for health research transfers, however, reveals extensive limitations to their utility. Whilst a full discussion of the

²⁷ As Christakis suggests of the situation following the ruling: ‘It is no longer sufficient for companies to “copy and paste” the SCCs template, “washing their hands” for what happens afterwards’. (33)

limitations on the use of each Article 49 justification in relation to health research is outside the scope of this paper, three general types of limitation should be highlighted.²⁸

First, the applicability of several Article 49 justifications, which superficially look relevant for health research transfers, is in fact unclear. This is the case, for example, in relation to the Article 49(1)(d) justification for ‘important reasons of public interest’. The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) explicitly recognises that the justification may be used to legitimate certain health research transfers in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic (35). There remains doubt, however, as to precisely which health research activities constitute important public interests. Previous guidance from the Article 29 Working Party (the forerunner to the EDPB) implied that ‘important’ public interests were to be distinguished from ‘ordinary’ public interests and were to be explicitly recognised by national law as such.²⁹ In this regard, Ploem et al. highlight that it may be difficult to qualify much health research under such elevated standards of public interest because ‘the potential of a research project to yield exceptionally important findings is hard to predict’. (37)

Second, even when a justification’s applicability is clear, all Article 49 options are subject to general conditions limiting their utility for health research transfers. In particular, the EDPB highlights: ‘[tier-three options] have to be interpreted in a way which does not contradict the . . . nature of [these options] as being exceptions from the rule’. (38). This position essentially makes clear that Article 49 justifications should not be used to justify run-of-the-mill health research transfers or open, ongoing research sharing arrangements. Interestingly, the EDPB also highlights

²⁸ Mitchell et. al. (34), however, do provide such an analysis. Mitchell et. al. discuss tier-three justifications in relation to genomic data. Their analysis, however, includes consideration of health research transfers.

²⁹ In relation to international transfers, the Working Party observed that the concept of ‘important public interest’ must be ‘given a restrictive interpretation’ and should only be considered to refer to processing which was ‘necessary and . . . identified as [an important public interest] by . . . national legislation’. (36)

that: ‘recourse to the derogations of Article 49 should never lead to a situation where fundamental rights might be breached’. (38) This statement implies that even Article 49 justifications cannot be used where third country legal systems cannot guarantee the standard of protection for EU citizens’ data equivalent to that elaborated in EU law. In the *Schrems II* case, however, the CJEU noted that Article 49 options may still be used to legitimate transfers to the US.³⁰ How the EDPB and the CJEU’s observations relate to one another is not fully clear.

Third, even when the applicability of an Article 49 justification is clear, and the general conditions for the application of Article 49 justifications can be met, each justification is then subject to specific criteria further limiting its utility for health research. To rely on the consent justification under 49(1)(a), for example, the GDPR requires that a research participant must be: ‘informed of the possible risks of such transfers...due to the absence of an adequacy decision and appropriate safeguards’. The EDPB suggests that this condition implies a subject can only consent to a specific transfer to a specific third country where the specific risks associated with the transfer can be made clear in advance. (38) This makes the consent justification awkward to rely on, for example, as regards personal data which has been collected without one or more specific transfer partners in mind.³¹

In light of the analysis in the previous sections as to the limitations to the legitimate transfer of personal data for health research purposes under the GDPR, an obvious question rears its head:

³⁰ Specifically, the Court highlighted the existence of Article 49 options as a reason that there was no legal gap left by the invalidation of the Privacy Shield agreement. See para 202: ‘As to whether it is appropriate to maintain the effects of that decision for the purposes of avoiding the creation of a legal vacuum . . . the Court notes that, in any event, in view of Article 49 of the GDPR, the annulment of an adequacy decision such as the Privacy Shield decision is not liable to create such a legal vacuum. That article details the conditions under which transfers of personal data to third countries may take place in the absence of an adequacy decision under Article 45(3) of the GDPR or appropriate safeguards under Article 46 of the GDPR.’

³¹ Mitchell et. al. (34) for example, partially in light of the limitation discussed, even go as far as to suggest consent under Article 49(1)(a) to be: ‘an extremely inflexible derogation to rely upon.’

how might the challenges posed by *Schrems II* for health research transfers be addressed moving forward? We suggest two different approaches that might provide solutions and facilitate international health research exchange between the EU and third countries. Our first approach consists of technical measures.

7. Technical Measures to Overcome Challenges

There are technical measures that do not involve actual data transfer, such as facilitating remote processing or remote access to data. Because these measures do not involve the active transfer of personal data outside the EU, they offer potentially new pathways that avoid the challenges posed to international transfers by the GDPR and its associated jurisprudence, including *Schrems II*. There are perhaps three commonly used technologies which facilitate international access to data without transfer of data. These techniques vary by the resources required to implement them, the governance structures in place around them, and the extent to which researchers can actually ‘access’ the personal data being processed.³²

First: remote access via a thin client (data visitation). A thin client is typically a low performance computer application that has been designed to establish a connection to a remote server, which does all the computing work itself. In this sense, we may conceptualise the thin client as an ‘enclave’ of the source jurisdiction, providing a window to the data stored at the source location whilst the data itself does not leave the source jurisdiction. Researchers access the data remotely to perform their analyses and may only retrieve (download) the results. Following the argumentation of the CJEU in the *Lindqvist* case, such an act of making data accessible may not

³² Examples of these approaches can already be seen in the social sciences, with a number of European nations sharing data via thin-clients. Note too that approvals by the host repository may also assume or impose local (target country) ethical approval requirements. When data is being shared internationally, there may need to be an agreement of ‘equivalence’ with regards to data security.

constitute an international transfer under the GDPR.³³ In addition, the source jurisdiction retains control of the outputs and can use techniques such as Statistical Disclosure Control to reduce the risk of data subjects being re-identified (40). However, whilst technical controls can limit the potential for actual transfer, a remote access solution may be vulnerable, depending on the access controls around the thin client itself and what is contained within the results returned to researchers. As such, it may be expedient to install thin clients within trusted repositories (or similarly accredited research data centres) in the third country which can safely manage access.³⁴

Second: access via remote execution. In a remote execution model, the data is not made available directly to researchers. Instead, researchers are given a codebook, or possibly a synthetic version of the data, that they can use to produce a code/script for the analysis they wish to perform. The code/script is then either submitted to the organisation hosting the data to run manually or as an automated job. The results of the execution are then assessed by the data hosts at the source location before being returned to the researchers. This removes the need for data to be transferred outside the source jurisdiction or for researchers in third countries to ever actually see the data. Data hosts will, however, need to ensure data is clean and that interfaces and fieldnames are well documented as it will be impossible for researchers to prepare to process the data without direct access to it.

³³ In the *Lindqvist* case, the CJEU recognised that merely making personal data stored in the EU accessible to a party in a third country, may not qualify as a transfer of data. '[T]here is no 'transfer . . . to a third country' where an individual in a Member State loads personal data onto an internet page which is stored with his hosting provider which is established in that State or in another Member State, thereby making those data accessible to anyone who connects to the internet, including people in a third country.'(39).

³⁴ Using data visitation to provide access to personal data can create significant burdens for data contributors and users accessing data in ensuring compliance with all relevant data privacy laws and clinical ethics or research ethics requirements. (41)

Third: a hybrid model. Infrastructure solutions, such as DataSHIELD, offer researchers greater flexibility compared to a remote execution model, but without the need to see the data as required by data visitation via a thin client (42). Researchers using these solutions are not able to see the underlying data, but receive anonymised results in real time – anonymised data do not qualify as personal data and therefore do not fall within the scope of the GDPR or its transfer provisions (see Recital 26). Such infrastructure can also offer federated solutions. The DataSHIELD platform, for example, can work with data housed in multiple locations (for example with clinical trial data from many countries) without data ever needing to be centralised. The entity responsible for the infrastructure then assumes responsibility for the appropriate governance surrounding the data they hold, but which may be federated across different research repositories.

Although technical solutions exist and are doubtless useful in facilitating health research exchanges where legal obstacles would otherwise make this difficult, each of these solutions exhibit limitations. Accordingly, it is important to highlight that these solutions cannot provide holistic answers.

8. Limitations of Technical Measures to Overcome Challenges

We would highlight three types of limitations on the utility of the proposed technical measures to facilitate international health research.

First, the proposed technical measures display scientific limitations. It is certainly the case that approaches such as data visitation and remote execution have great promise for enabling analyses pertaining to a single large data set - for example, in the analysis of patient outcomes in records held by one health care provider - as well as for certain types of ‘second-level’ analysis - for example, for a classic random-effects meta-analysis model. Other important research needs,

however, cannot be met using these measures. As outlined in section 2, above, the availability of personal data generally increases research efficiency and reduces bias. Data visitation and remote execution models permit access to personal data within one or more datasets kept by the data holder, but do not permit personal data to be exported and pooled.

Second, the proposed measures display practical limitations. For example, users of data visitation or remote execution systems will require skills training and support to work in systems provided by a data holder. This requires resource investment and available expertise on the part of the recipient researcher at the moment data need to be analysed. Equally, to ensure standards concerning the use of personal data are maintained, data visitation and remote execution systems require extensive governance and control systems, including, for example, the need for software certification and monitoring by trained professionals. The construction and maintenance of these systems is resource intensive and may further restrict possibilities for remote processing and analysis. Finally, to enable reproducibility, there remains a need for guidelines and standards for reporting analyses performed under data visitation and remote execution models such that results are reproducible by other researchers.

Third and last, the proposed measures display legal limitations. Pertinent legal definitions remain vague, disputed, and at times subject to swift and significant jurisprudential change. This means there are limits to the conviction with which technical measures can be proposed as solutions to legal problems. In the case of data visitation, the problem appears with the legal concept of ‘transfer’. The *Lindqvist* case is now almost two decades years old and scholars, such as Mitchell et. al. (34), have highlighted that the logic of the decision does not chime well with more recent

data protection thinking or jurisprudence.³⁵ Thus, the fact that personal data are viewed in a third country means they can indeed be argued to have been legally transferred to that third country even if they, technically, were only made accessible and never left the EU. In the case of remote execution and hybrid models, the problem appears with the definition of ‘personal data’ and the degree to which it is possible to provide synthetic data or anonymous data to third country researchers that is both scientifically useful and evades classification as ‘personal data’.³⁶

In light of the above, technical measures, whilst undoubtedly useful, may be inadequate to resolve all issues connected with current GDPR challenges to international health research data exchange. This recognition engenders a need to look elsewhere for solutions. In this regard, our second approach consists of a proposal concerning new policy measures.

9. Health Research Transfer Agreements to Overcome Challenges

The essential problem highlighted by *Schrems II* revolves around the lack of effective alignments between legal jurisdictions: whilst personal data *can* (technically) move freely, legal valuations and conditionalities attached to personal data *cannot*. To address this disjunct in the health research context, one option may be to consider health research transfers as unique forms of international data transfer and thus to consider the conclusion of unique bilateral and multilateral agreements

³⁵ As Mitchell et. al. (34) suggest in this regard: ‘The Lindqvist ‘mere accessibility’ proposition [is likely an] untenable distinction . . . in the present climate . . . [The] idea that the CJEU might again . . . [treat] personal data published to the world at large on a website and data transferred differently, seems out of step with the direction of the Court’s jurisprudence [sic].’

³⁶ There are significant divergences in opinions regarding the scope of the concept of personal data under the GDPR. Consider the differences in the following two approaches. On the one hand, the Article 29 Working Party took a hard line and suggested that any re-identification must be “‘reasonably’ impossible’. (43) On the other hand, the UK Information Commissioner’s Office foresaw the possibility for pseudonymised personal data, in some circumstances, to be considered anonymous. (44)

As an an example of the drastic swings in the definition of the concept in jurisprudence we would highlight the CJEU case of *Breyer*, in which the idea that certain legal restrictions on re-identification might serve to render data anonymous and therefore exclude its classification as personal data. The extent to which this is possible was not extensively discussed in the case and the idea has made few appearances in data protection jurisprudence since. (45)

outlining principles governing these transfers. Such agreements could serve to insulate health research transfers from problematic, jurisdiction-specific, legislation – as far as possible in light of regional legal and practical limitations. In turn, such agreements could be concluded where general transfer agreements cannot be concluded and could continue to function even where general transfer agreements fail.

Prior to sketching an argument in favour of such agreements, we should highlight a series of caveats to the proposal. In the first instance, we recognise that the idea of such instruments may be criticized as idealistic and as distant from current political and legal realities. In this regard, we recognise that such instruments are not likely to appear in the near future and certainly should not be looked to as providing short-term solutions. In turn, we recognise that numerous questions remain open concerning the substantive content of such agreements, as well as the procedures by which they could be concluded. Finally, even if the above issues were resolved, we recognise that such instruments would likely, in many circumstances, face significant obstacles to conclusion. Despite the above, we nevertheless consider the general idea as logical and interesting and seek here to open a discussion. In this regard, we sketch a four-pillar supporting argument.

First, the idea that health research transfers should be considered as a unique form of international transfer should not be received as strange. There is a general recognition that the interests, and conflicts of interests, engaged by health research are distinct from those which characterize other (usually commercial or bureaucratic) data processing contexts.³⁷ This is why the processing of personal data for health research is usually subject to separate legal and ethical conditions to those

³⁷ Indeed, authors such as Laurie recognise the constellation of interests engaged in health research might even be seen in terms of confluence rather than conflict - unlike in most other forms of processing. He states: 'this . . . does not seek to set interest against interest but seeks to bring about a confluence of public and private interests. In this sense it is a unique construct'. (46)

applicable to other processing purposes. This rationale is reflected in numerous international and national instruments outlining specific principles applicable to the use of personal data in health research – for example the World Medical Association’s Declaration of Taipei and the Estonian Human Genes Research Act (47). The rationale is even reflected in the GDPR, which outlines numerous (possible) exceptions to generally applicable principles relevant for health research - for example, the (possible) exemption to the purpose limitation principle in the second clause of Article 5(1)(b). If health research processing is generally treated as a unique type of data processing in ethics and law, then why not also for the purposes of international transfer agreements?

Second, we would suggest that the disadvantages to third countries’ non-research interests which, at least currently, would accrue from such agreements would likely, in many instances, be limited.³⁸ For example, should the EU and the US conclude a bilateral health research-specific transfer agreement implementing limitations on US intelligence services activities necessary to meet EU standards, we would suggest (albeit tentatively) that the negative impact on US national security interests would be nominal. To our knowledge, international data transfers for health research do not play a significant role in intelligence activities.³⁹ We know of no single case, for example, in which international health research data transfers have helped to secure any kind of arrest or prosecution.⁴⁰ Indeed, in this regard, most health research data seems unlikely even to be

³⁸ We restrict our proposition to the current situation given the speed of technological advance and the ability for data sets to be subjected to advanced analytical processes - including AI - capable of drawing novel and unexpected inferences about individuals and populations. We thus cannot exclude that, in future, data collected for health research will not take on a much more significant role in relation to other non-research state interests.

³⁹ We make this statement on the basis of information we are aware of concerning the issue. However, the issue has not been a topic of extensive empirical research and much law enforcement and intelligence activity is done without specific information ever being released to the public. We thus concede that it is, in principle, possible that international health research data transfers do play a significant role in law enforcement and intelligence services activity. This is a fascinating and worthwhile topic for further research.

⁴⁰ There are cases at national level in which locally collected health research data has been used in criminal investigations. Even these, however, to our knowledge, are limited in number. See, for example, the consideration of the use of research collections of biological samples and genetic data in law enforcement in (48).

of a type that will easily facilitate the novel insight into individuals' lives necessary for intelligence profiling.

Third, the benefit to health research may be significant. Under such agreements, researchers would be provided with access to personal data which was previously impossible and would be empowered to engage in the exchange of data for health research data with a minimum of legal obstruction – although other restrictions on transfers, such as proprietary restrictions, may still remain. Two other advantages would also present themselves: first, such instruments could mitigate against the risk that future jurisprudential developments concerning substantively different types of data transfer might impact the ability to engage in health research transfers – as was the case in *Schrems II*. Second, such instruments could be tailored specifically to the needs of health research and thus provide researchers with a clarity lacking in currently applicable international transfer provisions. In this regard, the scope and content of such instruments could be tailored to the needs and function of health research and could ameliorate uncertainties as to when transfers are legitimate and as to how they should be carried out.⁴¹

Finally, in terms of the content of such instruments, health research is, usually, already subject to strict ethical approval. Such approval may involve multiple agencies - such as a central health authority, an individual hospital or trust, and a research institution. The ethical principles which govern such approvals already seek to protect the interests, and fundamental rights, of research subjects and to balance these against the potential benefit of research for society as a whole. Although ethical governance must adhere to relevant legal instruments and principles, the fact that

⁴¹ Morrison et. al. (49), for example, highlight uncertainties connected with the transfer mechanisms outlined in Article 46 of the GDPR in relation to iPSC researchers and biobanking.

there is already such scrutiny in place in the health research context provides a precedent to limit and inform the policy measures as suggested here.

10. Conclusions

All transfers of personal data for health research purposes from the EU to third countries must be legitimated under one of the justifications outlined in EU data protection law under the GDPR. In principle, the GDPR outlines an extensive range of justifications relevant to health research. In the recent case of *Data Protection Commissioner v. Facebook Ireland Ltd, Maximilian Schrems (Schrems II)*, however, the CJEU made several pronouncements with significant consequences for the practical utility of these justifications for health research transfers.

Two assertions stand out. First, the CJEU invalidated the EU-US Privacy Shield adequacy decision. Second, the CJEU asserted that transfers based on any bilateral agreement between an EU transferor and a non-EU transferee would only be valid provided that the legal system to which the transferee is subject does not serve to undermine - irrespective of the bilateral agreement or any supplemental measures taken by the transferor - the standard of protection for personal data required by EU law in relation to the rights and freedoms of data subjects. This latter assertion has particularly wide-ranging implications for health research transfers.

From a legal perspective, the assertion is applicable to many of the justifications generally relevant, or potentially relevant, for the legitimation of international health research transfers under the GDPR - including contractual clauses, BCRs, codes of conduct and certification mechanisms. From a geographical perspective, the assertion is potentially relevant in relation to a large number of third countries. The required standard set by EU law is high and the legal systems in several

third countries - for example those of Canada, the UK and China - have already been criticised as possibly falling under this standard.

Certain justifications for the legitimization of international research transfers do remain largely unaffected by the *Schrems II* decision. The ruling in the case does not directly impact transfers on the basis of adequacy decisions - apart from on the basis of Privacy Shield - or those done on the basis of the specific situation justifications outlined in Article 49. The utility of these options for research transfers, however, is limited. There are only very few adequacy decisions currently in force. The possibilities furnished by Article 49 justifications can only be used in relation to limited types of health research transfers and even then only for limited sets of data transfers.

Moving forward, certain technical measures provide promising approaches to allow international health research involving personal data located in the EU to proceed despite legal obstacles. For example, remote execution models allow use of personal data in third countries whilst the personal data itself is never transferred outside the EU. As the data never leaves the EU, the approach is unaffected by problems pertaining to the GDPR's legitimate transfer provisions. Such technical solutions, however, have their own drawbacks and thus should not be considered a holistic approach to the facilitation of data exchange in international health research.

In this regard, policy measures may provide an alternative form of solution. In this regard, we would like to begin a discussion on the idea of research-specific international agreements, in which exemptions to problematic, jurisdiction-specific laws, might be pursued. The idea of research-specific transfer agreements would mirror the fact that research data processing generally enjoys

unique treatment in law. In turn, we believe that, in many cases, such research-specific agreements could be concluded at little disadvantage to pertinent EU or third country non-research interests, whilst providing significant impetus to health research and the outcomes of health research.

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